

ELLOS GROUP

SUSTAINABILITY REPORT
2015

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ABOUT THIS REPORT

This is Ellos Group's first sustainability report, covering our sustainability performance for the financial and calendar year 2015. We plan to continue sustainability reporting on an annual basis going forward.

The report is based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) guidelines, version G4, within accordance option Core. The content of this report is based on our materiality analysis, which includes stakeholder dialogue and value chain assessment.

This report covers the activities of Ellos Group, including its wholly owned subsidiaries, sales offices in Norway, Finland and Denmark and our headquarter and wholesale operations in Borås, Sweden.

No significant changes have occurred during the reporting period of this report.

This report has not been externally assured.

The Ellos Group sustainability report is available at the group website ellosgroup.com.

Annika Mårtensson,
Sustainability manager
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WORDS FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Sustainability is a key area for the fashion and home interior industry. Although the industry has accomplished a lot during the last years, regarding improvements in environmental performance and working conditions at the production units, several challenges remain.

We will most likely see an increased demand for materials with a better sustainability profile. This includes finding new production processes for cotton, but also developing new materials. New demands for recycling of products can be expected, driven by consumers and legislators. Increased transparency is another trend. In the future, the consumer might be able to compare environmental parameters of different products, for example water consumption and CO₂-emissions.

STRATEGIC IMPORTANCE OF SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability is an area of great strategic importance. To be competitive, we have to be sustainable. During 2013, Ellos Group started an extensive program to transform operations to e-commerce. This was when the current main owner acquired the company. New competence was added to the Board of Directors. The area of sustainability came under new light, not the least in the process to establish a framework for efficient corporate governance. This work has resulted in a number of policies and guidelines, among other things. These policies are often directly connected to sustainable development.

HIGH ON THE AGENDA OF THE BOARD OF DIRECTORS

In the work of the Board of Directors, each member must take sustainability into account in the decision making. This is logical, as sustainability is related to all areas in the operations of Ellos Group, from business strategies to tangible investments.

Over the next years, sustainable materials, sustainable value chain and monitoring will be high on the Board of Directors' agenda. The sustainability performance will be gradually integrated in the reporting, together with the key financial figures. We are convinced that sustainability and profitability are closely linked. The work to transform the Group is starting to show results. In combination with a clear sustainability agenda, there are good opportunities to grow sales with profitable results and, at the same time, make a significant contribution to society.

Finally, on the behalf of the Board of Directors, I would like to thank all employees for your dedicated efforts and hard work. This will be the foundation for the continued work for a sustainable Ellos Group.

*Anders Halvarsson,
Chairman of the Board, Ellos Group*

WORDS FROM THE CEO

Sustainability is an essential part of the long term value that we aim to create and of who we want to be – we want to contribute to a better world for future generations. But what does this mean in practice? Our approach to sustainability comes down to a way of acting in our daily business activities and in the choices that we make every day. Our strong corporate culture, with a strive to constantly improve performance is a solid foundation for sustainable development. A sustainable approach to business challenges us to be innovative, curious, transparent, and to contribute with our actions to the benefit of our customers, employees, business partners, owners, and to the communities in which we operate.

We operate in a rapidly changing world and we need to be proactive and agile to adapt to these changes, capture opportunities, mitigate risks, and continue building our business with a long-term perspective:

- **Digitalization and connected society** will challenge us to continually develop our business model, and will give us opportunities to improve our value chain, find new channels of business and communication, and to better understand and meet our consumers' needs. We also need to meet the increasing expectations regarding transparency from consumers and other stakeholders.
- **Globalization** will affect both consumer demands and the structure of our industry going forward. The competitive landscape will continue to evolve where online commerce is becoming increasingly global, and sourcing patterns may also change.
- **Climate change and scarce resources** are realities that we need to face by finding ways to reduce the use of energy and water and our greenhouse gas emissions. This may imply a move towards new materials, recycling and finding new and circular business models, but also to ensure an assortment with high quality and quality that lasts over time.

ACHIEVEMENTS IN 2015

In 2015, we have set the direction for our sustainability efforts and taken several steps to turn our ambition into action. You are now reading our first externally published sustainability report, which is one example of how we aim to increase the transparency and share our thoughts, efforts, goals, successes and challenges. We have taken a broad approach in this work, and I am impressed by the high level of commitment in our team to contribute.

We have reviewed our value chain, from design to consumer use and recycling, and identified opportunities and actions in many areas. We have collected input and feedback from a wide range of stakeholders, including 600 of our customers, to understand how we can best meet or exceed their expectations within sustainability. In our everyday work, we have among other things:

- *increasingly integrated sustainability thinking in design and materials choices;*
- *introduced an easier way for our customers to recycle their used garments;*
- *started mapping the energy use and emissions of our activities;*
- *joined Better Cotton Initiative (BCI) to support the development of better cotton production; and*
- *initiated new community engagement initiatives.*

There is no conflict between a sustainable development and value creation. It is a matter of continuous work to improve efficiency by utilizing existing resources in a better way and to build on the strengths that have made our company successful during almost 70 years. It is also important to keep an open mind, as we will need cooperation and partnerships, both with other companies and with society, to meet the challenges.

I would like to thank all employees for the significant steps we have taken on our sustainability journey during 2015. You are the most important resource in this company and you will be the ones who safeguard that Ellos Group will be a sustainable company also in the future.

*Hans Ohlsson,
CEO, Ellos Group*

ELLOS GROUP IN BRIEF

- Founded 1947 in Borås, Sweden
- The leading e-Commerce Group in the Nordic Countries within Fashion & Home Interior
- Head Office and logistic hub located in Viared outside of Borås, Sweden
- Majority owned by Nordic Capital since 2013
- Three online stores: Ellos, Jotex and Stayhard
- Sales and operations in the Nordic region; Sweden, Norway, Denmark and Finland
- Design and production of own brands, and over 400 external brands in the portfolio
- 2 BSEK turnover in 2015
- 800 employees
- More than 2 million active customers

For almost 70 years, Ellos Group has been making it easier for our customers to brighten up their day. This is what we will continue to do going forward.

Ellos Group is the leading e-Commerce Group in the Nordic Countries within Fashion & Home Interior. The portfolio of online stores consists of Ellos, Stayhard and Jotex, each a market leaders within their market segments. Ellos is the online department store for women, Jotex is the online home interior expert, and Stayhard is the leading fashion

destination for men. We continuously strive to develop market leading consumer brands and to build close relations with our customers. Our own brands are the foundation, supplemented in our assortment by selected external brands.

We are proud of the heritage of Ellos Group, which goes back to 1947 when Olle Blomqvist started Ellos. The cornerstone has been a strong entrepreneurial and merchant culture, that is still an important part of who we are. Over the years, the success

has been built on a close relationship with the customer, a passion to deliver value and to develop products and services.

During the past two years, Ellos Group has undertaken a major transformation, from a mail order business to a modern e-commerce player. We believe that the strong platform that we have built, as well as the ability to transform, will enable us to generate continued profitable and sustainable growth.

ellos

The Online Department Store for Women

Jotex
Hemtextilering för huset

The Home Textile & Decoration Specialist Online

STAYHARD

The nr 1 destination for Men's Fashion Online

SUSTAINABILITY AT ELLOS GROUP

Sustainability is a natural and value creating part of the daily business at Ellos Group. A sustainable business approach with a long-term perspective challenges us to be innovative, curious and transparent, and creates value to our customers, employees, business partners, owners as well as to the communities in which we operate. We want to contribute to a better world for future generations and aspire to build a business that can be part of the solution.

SUSTAINABILITY PRINCIPLES

Customers

We believe in transparency and a friendly, respectful and supportive communication. Our customers can always trust our generous advice as well as our products to be safe and responsibly produced.

The Team

We treat each other with mutual respect and provide equal opportunities in a healthy, safe and creative working environment. The competence, loyalty and entrepreneurial drive of our team enable us to reach our goals. Our key to success is constant progress.

Suppliers

We expect our suppliers and business partners to share our view on business ethics, human rights, fair working conditions and environment. We believe in co-operation and work with our suppliers to continually improve the sustainability of our value chain.

Environment

We strive to contribute to a sustainable future by using natural resources more efficiently and to minimize the negative environmental impact of our operations.

Community

We want to make positive contribution to the communities in which we operate by supporting chosen causes and initiatives that create a lasting difference, but always from a non-political and non-religious standpoint.

With our actions, we live these principles and build the reputation of a company that we can all be proud of. Our Code of Ethics and its supporting policies is an essential guide for us to ensure that we make the right decisions and take the right actions, including policies for anti-corruption, competition and data protection. Our whistleblowing policy prescribes how to report concerns, and how reported concerns are addressed.

SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES IN OUR VALUE CHAIN

The below illustration identifies important sustainability issues across our value chain. We have direct impact on the issues that are related to our local operations and our own employees, and on the design and purchasing of our assortment. Indirect sustainability issues are of high importance within our value chain, particularly within production and transport.

In production, we work with our suppliers and require their adherence to a detailed supplier's guide and code of conduct. We follow up through regular audits.

Our customers also have a large impact on sustainability in their care for our products, how long they keep them and whether they choose to recycle them after use.

We seek to influence our customers to a sustainable behaviour with clear washing instructions and by encouraging recycling.

OUR IMPACT						
DIRECT		INDIRECT		INDIRECT		
DESIGN PURCHASING	PRODUCTION	TRANSPORT	OPERATIONS	CUSTOMERS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mainly apparel and home interiors Own products 2/3 of sales 2015 External brands 1/3 of sales Approx. 9,000 own styles/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 171 core suppliers Main sourcing markets 2015: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> China 55% India 19% Bangladesh 8% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inbound freight from suppliers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea 90% Road 8% Air 2% Outbound freight to customers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 800 employees: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 765 in Borås Head Office and logistics 16 in Norway 17 in Finland 2 in Denmark 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2m active customers 4.7 m customer shipments 2015: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sweden 59% Finland 19% Norway 15% Denmark 7% 		
VALUE CHAIN ISSUES	ENVIRONMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable materials Chemicals Animal welfare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Chemicals Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emissions Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emissions Energy Waste Mailings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product care Recycling
	SOCIAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable materials Sustainable purchasing methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working conditions Human rights 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working conditions Equality and Diversity Employee Wellbeing 	
	Business Ethics and Anti-Corruption					
	Community Engagement					

Environmental issues are present across the value chain, while our key social issues are primarily related to production and operations.

Business ethics, anti-corruption and community engagement are topics that are relevant across the entire value chain.

STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE

In the past year, we have collected input and feedback from our most important stakeholders, seeking to understand which sustainability issues are important to them and why, what they expect from Ellos Group in terms of sustainability performance and communication, and how we can seek to meet their expectations. We have engaged more than 900 people in this process, covering current and potential customers, suppliers, owners and our local society, and we have gained insights that help us set priorities and focus our efforts going forward.

EMPLOYEES – Input: Employee survey, 200 responses, 38 interviews ¹
 Ellos Group’s employees show a very high level of interest in and commitment to sustainability, and believe that it is business critical.

CUSTOMERS – Input: Customer survey, 600 responses, 60 interviews, customer web panel ²
 Customers find sustainability increasingly important. They would like to have more information about Ellos Group’s sustainability work.

SUPPLIERS – Input: 4 Interviews ³
 Suppliers express high focus on sustainability, both from Ellos Group and other customers. In their view, Ellos Group should focus on value chain issues, including working conditions, sustainable materials and chain of custody of materials.

OWNERS – Input: 3 Interviews ⁴
 Owners expect the Group to deliver increased shareholder value. They take a long-term view on sustainability and are actively supporting the Group in sustainability matters. Focus on governance, managing risks and finding opportunities in the value chain.

SOCIETY - Input: 1 Interview ⁵
 Ellos Group is an important contributor to society in Borås, as the city’s second largest private employer and a supporter of several local community initiatives.

IMPORTANT SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES ACCORDING TO OUR STAKEHOLDERS

SOURCES:

1. Employee survey conducted Nov/Dec 2014, 212 responses. Interviews with 38 employees Nov/Dec 2014.
2. Consumer survey Nov/Dec 2014, sent to 8 000 Ellos, Jotex and Stayhard customers in Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Norway. 600 responses. received. Interviews in Gothenburg, Dec 2014. Customer web panel performed by Scandinfo with 26 participants.
3. Interviews: Bril Lacno, KGS, Henrik Wahlgren, Brink Textiles, and Tina Foghammar, Twist & Tango, Dec 2014, and Anders Rosén, C Jahn AB, Nov 2015
4. Interviews with Anders Halvarsson, Livehill, and David Samuelson, Nordic Capital, Dec 2014, and with Emma Brandt, Nordic Capital, Nov 2015
5. Interview with Anders Glemfelt, Enterprise relations manager, Borås Stad, Nov 2015.

MATERIALITY ANALYSIS

The focus within sustainability has been set based on the materiality analysis to secure we are covering the areas of utmost importance for our stakeholders and business.

The sustainability topics identified in the stakeholder dialogue and the value chain analysis were ranked in the two dimensions:

- **Stakeholder engagement** – Expectations and concerns among key stakeholders. What do our stakeholders care about?
- **Business impact** – Important sustainability issues in our value chain. What is the current or potential impact on Ellos Group’s business and financial performance, brand value and reputation?

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ↑	MEET EXPECTATIONS	FOCUS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recycling ▪ Customer mailings ▪ Chemicals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable raw materials ▪ Fair working conditions and human rights ▪ Anti-corruption and Business ethics
	MAINTAIN	DEVELOP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Community engagement ▪ Waste handling ▪ Employee wellbeing ▪ Sustainable purchasing process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy use and emissions ▪ Equality, Diversity and Inclusion ▪ Water management ▪ Animal welfare
		BUSINESS IMPACT →

In conclusion, the three issues of primary focus for our stakeholders, which also have a high business priority, are:

- **Sustainable raw materials** is a top rated issue for our customers, but also an important issue according to employees and suppliers. It is of high business relevance as an opportunity to improve customer satisfaction and business performance by offering our customers an attractive sustainable assortment and strengthening our brands.
- **Fair working conditions and human rights** are highly prioritized by stakeholders, mentioned top of mind by customers, employees, suppliers and owners. The potential business impact is significant, with a high reputational risk. Working with our value chain to mitigate risks and ensure compliance is challenging, given that our impact is indirect and that we need to manage a complex supply chain with a high number of suppliers in distant geographies.
- **Business ethics and anti-corruption** are deemed as very important by owners and employees, and mitigating risks in these areas is highly relevant to business performance. We need to ensure that appropriate policies are in place, communicated and implemented. We also need to ensure that our employees and business partners understand and adhere to the code of ethics.

SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

Our objective is to offer our customers an attractive assortment of products, that have been designed and produced in a sustainable manner. We can achieve this by making sustainable choices in design and purchasing, and by finding ways to increase the proportion of sustainable materials in our products.

ACTIONS 2015

- ✓ We have set the foundation for a significant increase of sustainable products in our offering.
- ✓ We have joined Better Cotton Initiative (BCI), through which we can contribute to a more sustainable cotton industry, and source sustainable cotton.
- ✓ We have joined Cotton Connect, where we contribute to the education of cotton farmers.
- ✓ We are developing our Conscious Choice assortment with new sustainable collections and brands.
- ✓ We are building organizational competence within sustainable materials and have significantly increased the materials training for design and purchasing and for suppliers and agents.

Our product assortment is a key focus area for our sustainability work – beginning with the design and the purchasing decisions that we make. Our design- and purchasing organization in Borås is the starting point for our own brand styles of mainly fashion and home interiors that we offer to our customers, accounting for about 2/3 of sales.

We have stringent standards for product safety, quality and chemicals, and our product policy defines materials that we exclude from all of our products, for example animal fur.

Going forward, we see an opportunity in moving towards more sustainable materials choices in our assortment. In 2015, we have taken several steps

in this direction. Our first focus area within sustainable materials is cotton. Cotton is, by a large margin, the most important fibre material in our textile assortment – some 78% of our own assortment product offering is cotton based (2015). It can also be defined as a raw material with high sustainability impact, including water use, chemicals and working conditions in production. Our target is that 100% of the cotton in our own products will come from sustainable sources by 2020.

Beginning our journey towards sustainable cotton, we have in 2014 and 2015 introduced some products with organic cotton, mainly within home textiles, kids, underwear and e-basics. Volumes, however, were still

modest, at 2% of purchased products 2014 and 3% in 2015.

In order to accelerate the move towards sustainable cotton, we joined Better Cotton Initiative (BCI) in 2015, through which we can source cotton that is produced with lower use of pesticides, less water use and better working conditions for the cotton farmers. We have also joined the Cotton Connect initiative, which contributes to the education of cotton farmers in sustainable methods.

Going forward, we will also seek to increase the use of other sustainable materials in our assortment, such as recycled fibres and innovative materials.

	2014	2015	Target 2020
Sustainable cotton, % of purchased cotton products*	2%	3%	100%

* Estimate based on manual data analysis. New systems to be implemented in 2016 will enable improved quality of tracking of materials going forward.

INDUSTRY INITIATIVES FOR SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

We believe in industry cooperation, and that by joining forces with others, we can have a stronger impact and achieve better results. We participate in the below initiatives relating to sustainable materials.

"The Better Cotton Initiative exists to make global cotton production better for the people who produce it, better for the environment it grows in and better for the sector's future. BCI aims to transform cotton production worldwide by developing Better Cotton as a sustainable mainstream commodity."
www.bettercotton.org

"CottonConnect is a pioneering company with a social purpose, delivering business benefits to retailers and brands by creating more sustainable cotton supply chains"
www.cottonconnect.org

"The Chemicals Group exists to disseminate the latest in chemical and environmental issues to member companies. Its aim is to convey the legal requirements and other easily comprehensible information on chemicals so that the information is used in companies' daily work with chemicals."
www.kemikaliegruppen.se

"The first objective of SSEI is to develop a tool/index that will help companies to reduce the environmental and social impacts for production of shoes. The second objective is to increase the knowledge about the environmental impacts in a life-cycle perspective for footwear at the participating companies/ organizations."
www.ssei.se

As members of BCI, we are working with CottonConnect, to contribute to a more sustainable cotton production process, with less pesticides, reduced use of water and better working conditions. We also appreciate the improved supply chain transparency, with traceability all the way back to the cotton farmers.

In November 2015, Lena Berger-Andersson, quality technician and environmental coordinator at Ellos Group, visited cotton farms in the villages of Rodh and Sarbhan in India with CottonConnect, and participated in training of farmers (right). She also visited a cotton ginner and a spinner with the CottonConnect team, including Patel Cotton Industries (left).

SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS ACCORDING TO ELLOS GROUP

- **Sustainable cotton**
organic, recycled or BCI Cotton
- **Organic fibres**
- **Recycled fibres**
- **Organic leather**
- **Innovated materials**
materials which through innovation has less environmental impact than conventional, through closed and controlled processes.

FUTURE FOCUS

- Participate actively with BCI and Cotton Connect programmes to support the development of sustainable cotton production.
- Build organizational capacity within sustainable materials choices through training and development of design, purchasing and customer service functions.
- Identify more sustainable materials and initiate co-operation with innovative suppliers.
- Implement the Swedish Shoe Environmental Initiative tool for sustainable material choices.
- Develop a definition and plan for sustainable wood.
- Develop our assortment of external brands with increased focus on sustainable products.
- Initiate the process of mapping the chain of custody of our products further back in the supply chain.

SUSTAINABLE ASSORTMENT – CLOSE by DENIM

CLOSE by DENIM is an Ellos Group brand, which has been built on the idea of more sustainable fashion

The brand started with a vision to produce jeans locally, in Borås, Sweden, and we seek to cooperate with local partners.

The garments are developed with a sustainable approach, including the choice of materials such as certified Eco denim for jeans.

Styles are meant to outlive trends and with attention to quality and craftsmanship, the CLOSE by DENIM garments are made to last longer.

SUSTAINABLE ASSORTMENT – CONSCIOUS CHOICE

Looks good, makes a difference

Our Conscious Choice assortment is produced with respect for people and the environment. We use materials that are better choices for the environment – organic, recycled or innovative materials.

Conscious Choice includes both basics and high fashion items – for everyday use and for special occasions.

ANIMAL WELFARE

Animal welfare is important to us. In our view, animals are, as sentient beings, entitled to be treated with respect. When our products are made of materials with animal origin, we require that the animals are treated well.

ELLOS GROUP:

- Does not sell products that contain real fur.
- Does not accept mulesing on merino sheep.
- Is restrictive in the usage of down and feathers and will only accept down and feathers as a by-product of meat. Live plucking is not accepted.
- Does not accept angora wool in any of our products.
- Will only accept leather as a by-product from meat.
- Only sells cosmetics that are not tested on animals.
- Does not sell products that contain materials which derive from endangered species.

We are members of:

CHEMICALS

We want to make sure that our products do not include any harmful, restricted or unnecessary chemicals. Our suppliers are required to follow strict regulations and tests are performed.

ELLOS GROUP:

- Does not sell products containing dangerous chemicals defined according to the regulations of the RoHS-directive and REACH regulation.
- Is restricted in using:
 - PVC, antibacterial additives, biocides, flame retardants and phthalates in textile products, leather or shoes.
 - Moisture preventing products and moisture absorbers to avoid mould, for example Silica gel.
 - Perfluorinated compounds (PFC) as water resistance/repellent treatment. PFC was phased out in own products in 2015.

We are members of:

SUSTAINABLE PURCHASING PROCESS

In addition to sustainable design and materials choices, our work processes also have other impacts on social and environmental sustainability in our value chain. With our move from mail order to an online business model, our product flow gets more evenly distributed throughout the year, with less sharp peaks and improved planning possibilities, which makes it easier for our suppliers to plan for capacity and meet our orders within normal work hours. The online business model also implies a move away from the catalogue "in-stock guarantee", due to which we have historically had to use air freight to fill inventory shortages. As we remove the in-stock guarantee in the beginning of 2016, emissions from air freight are likely to be reduced.

SUPPLIER RELATIONS

It is important to us and to our customers, employees and owners, that our products are made with respect to the people who produce them as well as to the environment. We strive to ensure fair working conditions and adherence to human rights in our value chain and believe that a close dialogue and cooperation with our suppliers is necessary to achieve this. Regular audits and inspections are means to follow up on progress and identify if improvement is needed.

ACTIONS 2015

- ✓ We have developed a new audit agreement with Bureau Veritas, with a new and more extensive audit program.
- ✓ We have defined the audit needs for suppliers, both through agents and direct suppliers, and increased the number of supplier audits conducted and planned in both channels.
- ✓ We have initiated a mapping of sub-suppliers, as a first step of improving control further back in our supply chain.
- ✓ We have started up five projects within the Swedish Textile Water Initiative.

Ellos Group's own brand products are manufactured by external suppliers, mainly in South East Asia. In 2015, we had 171 core suppliers, accounting for 91% of purchases.

Our main sourcing markets are China, India and Bangladesh, with 55% of order value in 2015 sourced from China, 19% from India and 8% from Bangladesh.

We want to make sure that the production of our products is done with safe and fair working conditions and adherence to human rights, and we seek to collaborate with our suppliers to ensure that they live up to our expectations. Our suppliers are required to sign and adhere to our Code of Conduct, and all core suppliers are inspected prior to first order.

We follow up on the working conditions, human rights and environmental status of our suppliers with regular inspections and audits, some of which are performed by our main agent KGS, and some through the independent audit institute Bureau Veritas. If improvement needs are identified in an audit, the supplier is required to implement improvements that are outlined in a Corrective Action Plan.

The number of independent audits of our suppliers has increased in the past couple of years, nearly doubling from 44 in 2014 to 77 in 2015. In the end of 2015, 49% of our core suppliers had been audited or inspected within 24 months, compared to 33% in 2014. By 2020, our target is for 100% of our core suppliers to have been audited, inspected or externally certified within 24 months.

CODE OF CONDUCT

- Our Code of Conduct is based on the French standard ICS (Initiative Clause Social), which is equivalent to programs such as BSCI (Business Social Compliance Initiative).
- We require all suppliers to sign the Code of Conduct prior to initiating any business relationship.
- Our goal is that all suppliers that manufacture our products are operating in adherence with the Code of Conduct.

ELLOS GROUP CODE OF CONDUCT

- **Child Labour:** Use of Child labour is not permissible. Workers can be no less than 15 years of age and should not be younger than mandatory age to be in school, in any given country.
- **Forced Labour and Prison Labour:** We prohibit recourse in any form what so ever to slavery, human trafficking, servitude for debt and forced or compulsory labour as well as to products or services created by this means.
- **Discrimination:** We recognize and respect cultural differences, and hence believe that workers should be employed on the basis of their ability to do the job. In that respect we prohibit discrimination, and in particular related to racial, age, ethnic, gender or sexual discrimination.
- **Disciplinary Practices, Harassment or Abuse:** All employees must be treated with respect and dignity. Under no circumstances do we accept our supplier's employees to be subject to ill treatment, coercion or corporal punishment – either physical or mental.
- **Freedom of Association:** We expect our suppliers to guarantee to their employees Freedom of Association and the right to join unions or other work or industry related associations as well as the right to collective bargaining in accordance with the local law.
- **Working Hours and Overtime:** We expect our suppliers to comply with legally mandated work hours.
- **Wages and Benefits:** Factories shall set working hours, wages and overtime pay in compliance with all applicable laws.
- **Environment, Health and Safety:** We will only do business with partners providing workers with a safe and healthy workplace. We also prefer to do business with partners who share our commitment to limit our impact on the environment.

SUPPLIER FOLLOW-UP PROCESS

We strive for all of our products to be manufactured in accordance with the Code of Conduct, under fair working conditions and with adherence to human rights. In order to track progress, identify risks and improvement opportunities, and to support our manufacturers, we have a control and follow-up system in place with regular audits and inspections.

Our main agent Kering Global Sourcing (KGS) conducts audits and inspections of the suppliers in their network, with a combination of own inspections and announced independent audits. All suppliers in

the KGS network have been inspected and approved prior to inclusion on the list of suppliers. For external audits, Bureau Veritas is used, both by KGS and by Ellos Group for merchandise bought through other suppliers.

Bureau Veritas utilizes protocols for on-site monitoring, which have been developed by KGS and Ellos Group. The new audit protocol, implemented in 2015, includes 233 compliance questions, compared to 109 questions in the previous protocol. Inspections include confidential employee interviews, record testing, observations and

management feedback. With a multipronged approach, monitors are able to consider various sources of information and utilize proven investigative techniques to corroborate evidence.

AUDITS AND INTERNAL ASSESSMENTS

The rate of external audits has increased significantly over the past two years, with the proportion of core suppliers that have been audited or internally assessed within 24 months at 49% in 2015, compared to 33% in 2014. We aim for 100% by 2020 and recognize a need to accelerate our supplier audits and inspections, and work closely with our agents to ensure that we reach this target.

	2014		2015	
	#	%	#	%
External audits < 2 years	44	26%	77	45%
Internal assessment < 2 years	12	7%	7	4%
Internal assessment 3-5 years	14	8%	15	9%
Not assessed <5 years	101	59%	72	42%

Sources: Bureau Veritas, Kering Global Sourcing (KGS)

Sources: Bureau Veritas, Kering Global Sourcing (KGS)

A COOPERATIVE APPROACH FOR SUPPLY CHAIN IMPROVEMENTS

The conclusions of external audits are weighed together to a rating, reflecting the supplier's performance on sustainability with a rating from A to D, as explained in more detail below.

In audits performed in 2013-2015, we see an improvement in audit results, with 58% of factories audited in 2015 rated A, up from

41% in 2014. We strive to increase the proportion of A and B ratings and to work with suppliers with lower ratings to improve their rating.

When improvement needs are identified, a Corrective Action Plan is issued, including a description of the non-compliance, recommended corrective action, a target date for when the corrective action is to be

completed and a comment from the factory. Depending on how serious the non-compliance is, another audit is scheduled to confirm progress within a set time frame. If issues are serious and not rectified, business may be terminated. In 2015, no suppliers were terminated due to serious non-compliance or failure to improve.

AUDIT STATUS BY COUNTRY OF SOURCING

By country of sourcing, we have the highest proportion of externally audited suppliers in Bangladesh, where 71% of our core suppliers are externally audited and rated A or B. We see room for improvement in China, where more external audits will be performed in 2016.

Sources: Bureau Veritas, Kering Global Sourcing (KGS)

SUPPLIER RELATIONS IN QUALITY ASSURANCE AND ENVIRONMENT

In addition to the efforts we make to ensure fair working conditions in our supply chain, we work closely with our suppliers and perform site visits and inspections to follow up on quality assurance and environment management of our suppliers. Environment management is audited within the Bureau Veritas audit protocol, as described on the previous pages.

Ellos Group cooperates closely with suppliers in proactive quality assurance through laboratory testing and inspections, ensuring that the products delivered to Ellos Group are already quality assured and that corrections or changes are made at the production site, before the

products are shipped to Sweden.

Laboratory tests are conducted, mainly by the accredited laboratories of Intertek, before production start on all main orders. The tests are based on instructions in our product specifications, with tests including general testing, mechanic resilience, colour fastness, dimensional stability and chemical tests.

Inspections are conducted by KGS on all of their orders, or by third party agencies, before shipping, to ensure that our quality requirements are met, and child security demands are met, in order to approve consignment before shipment.

SWEDEN TEXTILE WATER INITIATIVE– IMPROVING SUPPLIERS’ WATER MANAGEMENT

“Freshwater on our planet is precious. Sweden Textile Water Initiative brings together Swedish leather and textile companies in collaboration to reduce water, energy and chemical use in their supply chains.” (STWI.se)

It is estimated that 20 percent of industrial freshwater pollution is caused by the textile industry. The Sweden Textile Water Initiative was developed with this context in mind and with the aim of generating economic, social and environmental savings from sustainable water use in textile and leather production. Starting in 2011 as a small cluster group, STWI has grown to an initiative that works with over 100 factories in five major global production hubs, supplying 20 major Swedish brands.

In the period 2013-2015, STWI delivered impressive results by increasing the efficiency of resource consumption in a systematic, cost-efficient way through water reuse, pollution prevention, and effluent treatment.

The results are encouraging – in 2015, the STWI projects on average resulted in an 8% reduction in water use, 11% less energy used and a 6% reduction in chemicals used by the factories included.

Ellos Group currently works with five suppliers, one in India and four in Bangladesh. We strive to expand the project to more suppliers and to integrate STWI guidelines into our supplier audits by 2020.

In one of these factories in Bangladesh, water savings of 40,000m³ per year have been recorded, corresponding to the average annual water consumed by more than 2,400 people in Bangladesh.

(source: STWI and UNDP)

**SWEDEN
TEXTILE
WATER
INITIATIVE**

ENVIRONMENT

We strive to use natural resources efficiently and to minimise the negative environmental impact of our operations.

ACTIONS 2015

- ✓ We have Initiated analysis and tracking of the environmental impact of our operations, including energy use, CO₂ emissions, and recycling of waste.
- ✓ Based on improved understanding of our environmental impact, we have identified opportunities and initiated several actions to reduce energy use and emissions going forward.
- ✓ We have moved to electricity from renewable sources, significantly reducing the CO₂ emissions from operations.

We strive to reduce both energy use and emissions relative to sales. In 2015, we have initiated this process by beginning to measure our current status, understanding our biggest impacts, setting targets and taking actions to reduce energy use and emissions.

Our largest impact in terms of emissions is caused by the transport of our products from our suppliers to our warehouse, and on to our customers. Another important cause of emissions has historically been the

energy sources of electricity used in our head office and warehousing operations. By moving to 100% renewable energy in 2015, we have taken one important step in the right direction of reducing emissions from our operations. Within transports, we seek to minimise air freight and to work more proactively with our transporters to reduce emissions.

In connection with a major refurbishment of our head office, we will implement more energy efficient solutions for lighting and heating.

Other areas that we have addressed in 2015 include waste management, where we seek to increase the proportion of recycled waste.

Customer mailings is another area where we can reduce our environmental impact. The amount of paper mailings to customers has been reduced due to the removal of the traditional catalogue. There is further potential to reduce customer mailings by developing the online business model further.

		2015	2014	Change	Goal 2020
Energy use (MWh)	Electricity	6,657	6,786	-2%	To be determined in energy audit
	Heating	3,968	4,036	0%	
	Total	10,625	10,822	-1%	
Share of renewable electricity		71%	14%	57 ppts	100%
Greenhouse Gas emissions (CO ₂ tonnes)	Scope 2*	1,022	2,557	-60%	(see below)
	Scope 3*	7,167	6,613	+8%	
	Total Scope 2 + 3	8,189	9,171	-11%	
Greenhouse Gas emissions intensity: CO ₂ tonnes/MSEK sales		4.00	4.46	-10%	-20% vs. 2015
Waste: % recycled waste in HQ and warehouse		90.4%	89.5%	0.9 ppts	95%
Customer mailings, tonnes		7,352	9,069	-19%	-50% vs. 2015

* Scope 2: Indirect GHG emissions from consumption of purchased electricity, heat or steam.

Scope 3: Other indirect emissions, such as, transport-related activities in vehicles not owned or controlled by Ellos Group. Sources detailed in the following pages.

UNDERSTANDING AND ADDRESSING EMISSIONS

Inbound freight - the transport of products from our suppliers to the warehouse in Borås - is our largest source of greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for 57% of CO₂ emissions in 2015. Outbound freight to our customers account for 19% of emissions, while the electricity used in our operations generated 9% of our total CO₂.

The below table outlines the changes in CO₂ emissions from 2014 to 2015. Total emissions in 2015 decreased by 11% compared to 2014, driven by the move to renewable energy which led to a 66% reduction in the emissions from electricity. Emissions from inbound freight increased by 19% in 2015 due to higher volumes and a 20% increase in tonkm shipped. The average emissions per tonne and km shipped from inbound freight decreased by 1% year-on-year, to 36 g/tonkm.

Outbound freight emissions have decreased by 16% in 2015 due to a change in product mix, to fewer and bigger packages, and a reduction in the number of returns.

Business travel increased in the year, leading to 27% higher emissions.

CO ₂ , tonnes	2015	2014	Change	Change %	Comment
Heating	222	223	-1	0%	
Electricity	799	2,334	-1,535	-66%	Change to renewable energy
Subtotal Scope 2	1,022	2,557	-1,536	-60%	
Inbound	5,143	4,328	815	19%	Increased volumes
Outbound	1,711	2,039	-328	-16%	Product mix change
Business travel	312	246	66	27%	Increased travel
Subtotal Scope 3	7,167	6,613	554	8%	
Total	8,189	9,171	-982	-11%	
CO ₂ g/SEK sales	4.00	4.46	-0.50	-11%	

Greenhouse Gas emission scopes as defined by GHG protocol, ghgprotocol.org

Scope 2:
Indirect GHG emissions from consumption of purchased electricity, heat or steam.

Scope 3:
Other indirect emissions, such as, transport-related activities in vehicles not owned or controlled by Ellos Group.

Sources:
 Electricity and heat: Borås Energi, Göteborgs Energi, Din El, Energimarknadsinstitutet
 Inbound freight: Transport suppliers
 Outbound freight: Postnord, DHL, Ellos Group estimates for returns.
 Travel: AKI travel, Resia

IDENTIFYING ENERGY SAVINGS OPPORTUNITIES

From 2010 to 2015, use of energy for electricity and heating at the Head Office and warehouse operations has fluctuated within a range of 10.2- 11.2 GWh. In 2015, energy use ended in the middle of this range, at 10.6 GWh, translating into a year-on-year decrease of 1% compared to 2014. Energy use in relation to net sales, was 5.19 MWh/MSEK, a 2% decrease from 5.28 MWh/MSEK in 2014.

An energy audit has been initiated, in accordance with the EU Energy Efficiency Directive. Based on this review, we will identify energy savings opportunities and set targets for reduced energy use for the coming years.

We are in the process of rebuilding our Head Office, in connection with which we will implement some energy saving initiatives, which we expect to reduce our energy use from 2017. In 2016, we might see increased use of energy due to the on-going building work.

CHANGE TO RENEWABLE ENERGY

As of April 2015, Ellos Group moved to 100% renewable energy, reducing the CO₂ emissions from electricity from 344 g/kWh in 2014 to an estimated 120 g/kWh 2015 and 5 g/kWh in 2016. Prior to the change of source, Ellos Group's electricity sources corresponded to the Nordic markets' residual mix.

INCREASING BUSINESS TRAVEL

Business travel at Ellos Group increased in 2015, from 1,176 one-way trips in 2014 to 2,101 in 2015, translating into emissions of 312 tonnes of CO₂ in 2015, mainly from air travel. To a certain extent, air travel is necessary in order to oversee for example production and purchasing offices in the Far East, where replacing air with other means of transportation is not practically feasible. For shorter distances, however, we can encourage our employees to travel by train.

	2015	2014	Change	Change %
Number of trips	2,101	1,176	925	79%
- of which air	1,857	991	866	87%
- of which train	244	185	59	32%
CO ₂ tonnes	312	246	66	27%

Sources: AKI travel, Resia

EMISSIONS FROM TRANSPORT

INBOUND FREIGHT

In 2015, Ellos Group's total inbound shipments of products from our suppliers increased by 20% to 145 million tonkm. Total CO₂e emissions from inbound freight increased at a similar rate, by 19% to 5,232 tonnes, translating into emissions per tonkm of 36 g, 1% down from the 2014 level.

We seek to maximise the use of sea freight, which has significantly lower emission levels than air, at 13 g/tonkm versus 739 g/tonkm for air freight in 2015. Sea freight accounted for 90% of tonkm shipments in 2015, followed by truck at 8%. Air

freight accounted for only 2% of tonkm freight in 2015, and generated 40% of Ellos Group's inbound freight emissions.

We will strive to minimize air freights going forward, and expect a decrease in the coming years as we will phase out backorders. We will also seek closer cooperation with our freight partners to reduce emissions, with environmental guidelines, emission limits and benchmarks.

INBOUND FREIGHT SPLIT, % TONKM

EMISSION SPLIT, % CO₂e

Sources: Geodis, Damco, Kuehne, DSV Air&Sea, Toll, DHL, Transbaltika, ALPI, Schenker, Freja, NTEX, Fedex, ScanLog

OUTBOUND FREIGHT

In 2014, we made 5.1 million shipments to our customers in the Nordic countries.

The average CO₂ emissions per shipment was 0.30 kg. Emissions are higher in Finland compared to the other countries due to the longer distance from our warehouse.

Between 2014 and 2015, the number of packages sent to customers decreased by 7%, but with an 8% higher average weight due to changes in our product mix and fewer returns. While we shipped a similar number of kilos, these changes led to a 16% decrease in CO₂ emissions compared to 2014.

We continuously seek to optimise freight planning and filling rate in transport vehicles. Going forward, we will increasingly work proactively with freight providers, with environmental requirements as a part of the purchasing process.

	Number of shipments	Total shipped weight, kg	Average kg/shipment	Emissions kg CO ₂ total	CO ₂ /shipment	CO ₂ /kg
Sweden	2,931,508	5,922,000	2.02	630,101	0.21	0.11
Norway	737,000	1,491,600	2.02	128,000	0.17	0.09
Denmark	353,000	555,000	1.57	144,000	0.41	0.26
Finland	1,040,000	2,185,000	2.10	598,000	0.58	0.27
Returns				211,129		
Total	5,061,508	10,153,600	2.01	1,711,230	0.30	0.15

	2015	2014	Change	Change %
Total number of shipments	5,061,508	5,467,064	-405,556	-7%
Average shipment weight, kg	2.01	1.85	0.15	8%
Total shipped weight, kg	10,153,600	10,130,509	23,091	0%
Total CO ₂ from outbound freight, kg	1,711,230	2,038,923	-327,693	-16%

Sources: : Postnord, DHL, Ellos Group estimates for returns.

WASTE HANDLING

RECYCLING OF WASTE IN OUR OPERATIONS

Yearly waste volumes, tonnes	2015	2014	Change	Change %
Corrugated paper	628	860	-232	-27%
Wood	131	140	-9	-6%
Metal	31	37	-6	-16%
Office paper	30	34	-3	-10%
Polyethene	11	25	-14	-56%
Other	0	17	-17	-100%
Subtotal recycled	831	1 112	-282	-25%
			0	
Incinerable waste	69	111	-42	-38%
Unsorted waste	15	19	-3	-18%
Landfill	4	1	3	259%
Subtotal not recycled	88	130	-43	-33%
			0	
Total	918	1,243	-324	-26%
Recycled, % of total waste	90.4%	89.5%		

Sources: AD Infinitum, Borås Energi & Miljö

Our waste mainly derives from the logistics operations, and 90% of the waste that we generate is sorted into fractions and recycled. We aim to further improve sorting into fractions and recycling, to recycle 95% of waste in 2020.

The total amount of waste in our Borås logistics operations and head office was 918 tonnes in 2015, a decrease of 26% from the previous year. Corrugated paper is by far the largest category at 68% of total waste volumes 2015. A total of 88 tonnes, or 10% of the total waste volume, was not recycled in 2015. Most of this, 69 tonnes, was incinerated to generate district heating.

ENCOURAGING OUR CUSTOMERS TO RECYCLE

One of the challenges of the apparel and home textile industry is to persuade consumers to recycle their textiles. Only in Sweden, 70,000 tonnes of textiles end up as incinerated household garbage every year, corresponding to 8 kilos per capita, according to the Swedish Society for Nature Conservation (SSNC).

Given our online business model, we have partnered with Cirqle, to encourage and incentivize our customers to recycle their used textiles. The Cirqle app guides the customers to one of 51 collection points of non-profit organizations in 21 towns across Sweden, where they can leave used clothes and home textiles. As a reward, the customer receives a reward from Ellos Group.

ENVIRONMENT INITIATIVES IN OPERATIONS

CUSTOMER MAILINGS

- By 2020, we aim for a 50% reduction in our mailing of printed matters to customers, compared to 2015. We also strive for 100% of paper mailings to be PEFC- or FSC-certified and for 100% of printing houses used to be certified by Nordic Ecolabel or similar.
- From 2013 till 2015, we have already reduced our paper mailings by approximately 40%, or 5 000 tonnes, which corresponds to about 30,000 trees or a forest area of 30 football fields each year.
- The reduction is made possible by the transition to an online business model and improved tailoring of communication to our customers' needs. .
- Today, our magalogs are printed on PEFC-certified paper, and 70% of our other mailings are printed in Nordic Ecolabel-certified printing houses.

FOOD

At the Head Office in Borås, the personnel restaurant is managed by Eurest, a part of the Compass Group. Together with them, we have identified improvement areas:

- We have replaced coffee milk in small plastic containers in with litre-packages of organic milk. Besides the move to organic, this saves a large amount of plastic packaging – one 1 litre package corresponds to 50 plastic containers, totalling approximately 85,000 containers annually (based on our own calculations), which to a large extent were not recycled.
- We have introduced organic bananas and Fairtrade coffee.
- Communication has been improved, highlighting organic coffee, milk and eggs and Swedish chicken offered in the restaurant.
- There is also more information highlighting how everyone can contribute, by separating waste and avoiding to throw away food. The restaurant has arranged a fair trade event, and sustainability weeks, highlighting sustainable food choices and actions.

PACKAGING

- Our deliveries to customers are made in a packaging made of plastic, which is efficient from a transportation space perspective if compared to e.g. paper cartons.
- A new plastic packaging to customers has been developed during 2015, to be launched in 2016, with the environmental aspect in mind. The plastic material in the bags will be changed from virgin to recycled polythene.
- On an annual basis, Ellos Group uses 3.5 million packaging bags.

EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY

Ellos Group aspires to be a modern and attractive workplace. In order to achieve this, we need to offer good working conditions, strong leadership, and a diverse workforce in terms of ethnic background, culture, gender and age. An inclusive corporate culture, in which we accept and leverage differences, is a prerequisite for an efficient, professional and profitable business, and an important component when we seek to recruit, develop and retain the right competence. In Ellos Group, all employees shall have the same opportunities, rights and responsibilities, regardless of gender, gender identity or expression, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religion, disability or age.

ACTIONS 2015

- ✓ Analysis of the current status, both in terms of gender and ethnic diversity
- ✓ Update of Equality & Diversity Policy
- ✓ Targets set for Equality and Diversity
- ✓ Strategies developed, with broad-based organizational input and involvement

OUR EMPLOYEES

In December 2015, Ellos Group had a total of 641 permanent employees, 606 of which are based in the Borås headquarters and logistics operations. We have 16 employees in Norway, 17 in Finland and 2 in Denmark.

In addition to the permanent employees, we also employ around 150 temporary employees, of which the majority are students who work during holidays and weekends, mainly in the logistics operations.

	% Women	% Men
All Employees	67%	33%
Managers	45%	55%
Senior Management Team	23%	77%
Board of Directors	50%	50%

STRIVING FOR GENDER EQUALITY AT ALL LEVELS

We strive for even gender representation in the organization. This is important for us in order to be an attractive employer, and to create the best working environment and a high performing team. Our target is to have an even gender representation in management, across departments and management levels by 2018.

As of December 31 2015, a clear majority of our employees were female, 67% of the workforce. Among managers, 55% were men and 45% women. Our Board of Directors was evenly split between men and women, while we had a higher proportion of men in the Executive Committee (100% male) and the Senior Management Team (77% male).

Striving to reach our goal in 2018, we will work actively with identifying and supporting female employees with potential and ambition to be promoted to management. We will also establish a broad-based working group for equality and diversity, and work to ensure that recruiting processes support our ambition.

TARGETS FOR EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY

- Even gender representation in management, across departments and management levels. Manager split 50/50 male/female by 2018.
- Increase the proportion of employees with foreign background (from 12,7%), across departments and management levels, to better reflect society (Borås currently at 27%).

PROMOTING DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

Ellos Group's operations is based on an open and inclusive attitude, where diversity and equality add value and where discrimination is not accepted. For us, diversity means a mixed group of employees with different gender, gender identity or expression, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religion, disability and age. We are convinced that encouraging and leveraging differences will benefit our business, through a better understanding of our customers, more creativity and innovation, improved problem solving ability and a more interesting and dynamic workplace.

Besides gender equality, we have focused on ethnic diversity as the first priority for our defined diversity targets. Our long term target is for the ethnic diversity of our organization to reflect the society in which we operate.

Based on input from Statistiska Centralbyrån (SCB), we have conducted a current status analysis with focus on the ethnic diversity of our workforce in Sweden. The conclusion is that people with foreign background are currently underrepresented, at 12.7% of the workforce, compared to the demographics in the society of Borås, at 27%. Our goal is to increase the proportion of employees with foreign background, across departments and management levels, to better reflect the society.

■ Foreign background
■ Swedish background

Source: SCB, Borås Stad

EMPLOYEE WELLBEING

At Ellos Group, we continuously strive to attract, develop and retain competent and motivated employees. A health promoting way of working is therefore a priority for Ellos Group. We work proactively to create a safe and healthy working environment and also to promote a healthy lifestyle among our employees.

EMPLOYEE SURVEY

Ellos Group's employees are a very important factor for our success. Therefore it is key for Ellos Group to continuously evaluate how we are doing as an employer, and how we can become even better. An employee survey helps us to create a platform for dialogue, transparency and openness, which are important parts of our corporate culture and core values. An employee survey is conducted on a bi-annual basis, and was performed in 2015 with a response rate of 87%. Starting in 2015, we have chosen a new provider of this survey, with improved measures and tools. Due to this change, we do not have comparable historic data for the survey. The 2015 results were as follows.

E-NPS

This measure tells us to which extent our employees would recommend the company as a place to work – attractive employer. Survey respondents are defined as ambassadors, passive or critics. The e-NPS is calculated as the percentage points of employees that are ambassadors minus the percentage points that are critics, and can range from -100 to +100. Ellos Group was rated +15, compared to the external benchmark of +7. Our target is to reach +20 in the next employee survey that will be conducted in 2017.

EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION INDEX

This index includes questions about the following areas: respect, cooperation, impact, feedback, trust, information, holistic view, objectives, personal development, implementation and follow-up.

The Ellos Group rating 2015 was 82, which is a good rating, although there is still some room for improvement to the external benchmark at 86.

PROACTIVE HEALTH PROMOTION AT ELLOS GROUP

HEALTH AND WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Ellos Group has a long tradition of working strategically with employee health. Our vision is for all employees to feel better. Our proactive health improvement efforts include a health survey, which is conducted in all departments, with the aim to cover the entire group within a two-year period. Based on the survey, a plan is developed for how to improve health in the department. Individuals that would benefit from a healthier lifestyle and motivation are offered personal health coaching.

Ellos Group offers its employees a wide range of activities to encourage a healthy lifestyle. Among other things, we participate in an annual exercise challenge. There is a clear correlation between more exercise and less sick leave, which gives us a strong incentive to continue our work to motivate more employees to exercise regularly.

CONTINUOUS EFFORTS TO MINIMIZE SICK LEAVE AND WORK RELATED INJURIES

We continuously follow up on the level of sick leave and aim to reduce sick leave with clear routines for following up and acting on reasons for absence.

	Sick leave, % of ordinary work hours
2013	5.14%
2014	4.78%
2015	5.38%

We track and follow up on all work related injuries and incidents, seeking to minimize injuries by addressing risk areas.

The below table quantifies the number of work related injuries and reported incidents at the workplace, which did not lead to any personal injuries. We report and follow up incidents that could have led to injuries, to ensure that potential risks are addressed. The most common work related injuries are related to back- neck- and shoulder problems, where we seek to improve workplace ergonomics to mitigate the number of injuries.

	Work related injuries	Reported incidents
2014	26	41
2015	20	34

2015 AWARDS AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

"THE BEST WORKPLACE IN RETAIL 2015"
 Ellos Group won the 2015 award of the Union of Commercial Employees as "The best workplace in retail", with the following explanatory statement:
"Ellos Group is a workplace where employees, union representatives and managers have the ability, the will and the ambition to together contribute to a positive development for all parties involved. Ellos Group is a workplace that makes a difference."

"SUPER-ROCKET OF THE YEAR"
 Ellos Group was appointed "Super-Rocket" of the year 2015 in the student ranking performed by Universum, ranked at position 84, up from position 124 in the previous year.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

We want to make positive contribution to the society in which we operate. We focus on supporting charitable causes and sponsorship programmes that are relevant to our employees, to our value chain and to our customers.

WE SUPPORT INITIATIVES...

- ✓ in societies touched by our value chain
- ✓ in which we can take an active part as a sponsor and where our employees can be involved
- ✓ that are driven by entrepreneurship and innovation
- ✓ that support the wellbeing and education of children and young people
- ✓ that are connected to our core competences
- ✓ that are relevant to our Brands.

RECENT COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT INITIATIVES

"LANGUAGE FRIENDS"

Our local society currently has a big challenge in integrating immigrants, a challenge which is getting bigger with the large current inflow of refugees. A key factor in order to get established in society is to learn the language. Many immigrants lack connections to native Swedish speaking people to practice and develop their speaking skills.

In cooperation with Borås Stad, Ellos Group has launched a program, in which we invite a group of immigrants to regularly come to our office, have lunch, and practice their Swedish with "language friends" among Ellos Group employees. So far, 30 of our employees have become language friends to 20 immigrants, in meetings that have proven an equally valuable experience for both parties.

ONE BRACELET

Ellos Group has taken an active standpoint for women's equal rights and against discrimination and violence against women, by being the first online company selling "One bracelet" supporting UN women.

"Wear it with a meaning for women's equal rights"

KISS

KISS, or Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences, is a school in Odisha, one of the poorest parts of India. KISS fights poverty through education of children from underprivileged backgrounds, and currently enrolls 25 000 students, also providing free housing, meals and health care. The success of the program has led to cooperation with Unicef and UNESCO and an advisory status in the UN. For Ellos, the support to KISS is a way to contribute in an important country for sourcing. There is also a connection to Borås, where the Swedish branch was founded by a former student of the school (who became famous when riding his bike all the way from India to Sweden to reunite with the love of his life).

GRI INDEX

REQUIRED DISCLOSURES			
		DISCLOSURE	PAGE AND/OR COMMENT
STRATEGY AND ANALYSIS		G4-1	p. 3-4, Word from Chairman & CEO
ORGANIZATIONAL PROFILE		G4-3-10, 13, 17	p. 5, Ellos Group in brief p. 25, Equality and diversity
		G4-11	All employees covered by collective bargaining
		G4-12	p. 7, Value chain
		G4-14	p. 10-13, Sustainable assortment
		G4-15, 16	p. 11, Industry initiatives p. 13, Animal welfare
IDENTIFIED MATERIAL ASPECTS AND BOUNDARIES		G4-18-21	p. 8-10, Stakeholders, value chain and materiality
		G4-22, 23	No - not applicable (this is our first report)
STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT		G4-24-27	p. 8, Stakeholder dialogue
REPORT PROFILE		G4-28-33	p. 2, About this report
GOVERNANCE		G4-34	See www.ellosgroup.com
ETHICS AND INTEGRITY		G4-56, 58	p. 6, Sustainability principles
MATERIAL ASPECT DISCLOSURES			
CATEGORY	ASPECT	DISCLOSURE	PAGE AND/OR COMMENT
ENVIRONMENT	MATERIALS	G4-DMA, EN1	p. 10, Sustainable materials
		G4-EN2	0% of product materials used 2015 are recycled input materials.
	ENERGY	G4-DMA, EN3, 5, 6	p. 21, Energy savings opportunities
	EMISSIONS	G4-DMA, EN16-19	p. 20, Understanding and addressing emissions
	EFFLUENTS AND WASTE	G4-DMA, EN23	p. 23, Recycling of waste in our operations
	TRANSPORT	G4-DMA, EN30	p. 22, Emissions from transport p. 21, Business travel
SOCIAL	TRAINING AND EDUCATION	G4-DMA, LA6	p. 28, Proactive health promotion
		G4-LA11	100% of employees receive regular performance and career development reviews,
	DIVERSITY AND EQUAL OPPORTUNITY	G4-DMA, LA12	p.25-26, Equality and diversity
	SUPPLIER ASSESSMENT FOR LABOR PRACTICES	G4-DMA, LA14, 15	p. 14-18, Supplier relations
SUB-CATEGORY: HUMAN RIGHTS	FREEDOM OF ASSOCIATION AND COLLECTIVE BARGAINING	G4-DMA, G4-HR4	p. 14-18, Supplier relations
	CHILD LABOR	G4-DMA, G4-HR5	
	FORCED OR COMPULSORY LABOR	G4-DMA, G4-HR6	
	ASSESSMENT	G4-DMA, G4-HR9	
	SUPPLIER HUMAN RIGHTS ASSESSMENT	G4-DMA, G4-HR10	